

D5.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan and Exploitation Strategy

Work package	WP5 Dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement
Task	T5.1 Dissemination and communication strategy and activities T5.4 COcyber stakeholder engagement and Ambassador Programme
Due date	31-12-2024
Submission date	09-12-2024
Deliverable lead	AUSTRALO
Version	v0.1
Authors	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
Reviewers	Palina Shauchuk, Nicolas Ameye (ULB), Frederico Iannuli (LC)

Abstract

The plan sets out a strategy to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders. It outlines the target groups and their segments, presents key messages, tools and channels used, as well as the ambassador programme methodology.

Keywords

Dissemination, Communication, Stakeholder Engagement, Ambassador Programme, Sustainability, Marketing, Branding, Impact.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	11.11.2024	Table of Contents	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
v0.2	19.11.2024	Section 5	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
v0.3	26.11.2024	Sections 1 and 2	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
v0.4	28.11.2024	Sections 3 and 4	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
v0.5	03.12.2024	Final adjustments for internal review	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)
v0.6	04.12.2024	Review 1	Frederico Iannuli (LC)
v0.7	04.12.2024	Review 2	Palina Shauchuk, Nicolas Ameye (ULB)
FINAL	09.12.2024	Final version for submission	Mona Marill (AUSTRALO)

Disclaimer

The COcyber project funded under Grant Agreement No. 101158606 is supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre and funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre can be held responsible for them.

The contents of this deliverable are presented for informational purposes only and are subject to the pending approval of the European Commission (EC). The information, data, and conclusions presented herein may undergo revisions or modifications following the review and approval process by the European Commission. Recipients of this document are advised that any actions, decisions, or reliance on the information provided should be exercised with caution until the final approval from the European Commission is obtained. The authors and distributors of this deliverable shall not be held liable for any consequences arising from the use of information that has not yet received official European Commission approval.

Copyright notice

© COcyber 2024-2026

Project funded by the European Commission in the Digital Europe Programme

to specify: R, DEM, DEC, OTHER*

Public – fully open. e.g., website

Sensitive (SEN) – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

EU classified – RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).
DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.
DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations.....	6
Executive Summary.....	7
Introduction.....	8
1.1 Structure of the report.....	8
1.2 Related tasks and deliverables.....	9
2 COcyber Stakeholders.....	10
2.1 Definition of the target stakeholders.....	10
2.2 Stakeholder Engagement Tactics.....	11
3 Communication and Dissemination Plan.....	14
3.1 Communication Strategy.....	14
3.1.1 Objectives.....	15
3.1.2 Communication phases.....	16
3.1.3 Measures.....	18
3.2 Dissemination Strategy.....	26
3.2.1 Objectives.....	26
3.2.2 Dissemination phases.....	27
3.2.3 Measures.....	28
3.3 Activity Monitoring and Risk Mitigation.....	30
3.3.1 Monitoring strategy.....	30
3.3.2 Possible Risks.....	31
4 COcyber Ambassador Programme Strategy.....	33
4.1 Overview of the objectives.....	33
4.2 Ambassador Programme Structure.....	34
4.2.1 Three batches of Ambassadorships.....	34
4.2.2 Ambassador Profiles.....	35

4.2.3	Ambassadors’ Duties	36
4.3	Selection to the Ambassador Programme	38
4.3.1	Eligibility Criteria	38
4.3.2	Scouting and Evaluation Process	39
4.4	Ambassador Programme Timeline	41
4.5	Other important aspects	42
4.5.1	Acknowledgement of EU finding and disclaimer	42
4.5.2	Conflict of interests	43
4.5.3	Communication about the programme	43
5	Exploitation Plan.....	44
5.1	Key Exploitable Results	44
5.2	Exploitation and Sustainability Principles	44
6	Conclusion and Next Steps.....	46
	Annex 1 – Editorial plan for blog articles in Year 1.....	48
	Annex 2 – Gantt Chart of the Ambassador Programme.....	50

List of Figures

Figure 1	COcyber Stakeholder Groups.....	10
Figure 2	COcyber's communication funnel.....	14
Figure 3	Communication in three phases	17
Figure 4	COcyber Brandbook Cover	18
Figure 5	COcyber Colors Scheme	19
Figure 6	COcyber Logo formats	19
Figure 7	COcyber Header Banner	19
Figure 8	COcyber Roll-Up Banner.....	20
Figure 9	COcyber marketing flyer	21
Figure 10	COcyber email signature	21
Figure 11	A glimpse of the COcyber platform.....	24
Figure 12	COcyber dissemination phases	27
Figure 13	Communication and dissemination cycle.....	31
Figure 14	COcyber Ambassador's Journey.....	34
Figure 15	Ambassador Programme Batches.....	35
Figure 16	COcyber Ambassador's mission.....	37
Figure 17	EU Logos for acknowledgement of funding.....	43
Figure 18	Ambassador Programme Logo.....	43
Figure 19	Ambassador Batch Visual Banners.....	43
Figure 20	Exploitation models.....	44
Figure 21	Tools to sustain the project in time.....	45

List of Tables

Table 1 Main benefits by major target group.....	12
Table 2 Communication objectives per target group.....	15
Table 3 KPIs for Communication.....	16
Table 4 COcyber communication tools.....	23
Table 5 COcyber KPIs for Dissemination.....	27
Table 6 COcyber's measures for dissemination.....	28
Table 7 Dissemination & Communication Risks.....	32
Table 8 Relevant Ambassador Profiles.....	35
Table 9 Key Performance Indicators for monitoring the ambassadors' mission.....	37
Table 10 Following Score Range.....	39
Table 11 Fit to the Position Score Range.....	40
Table 12 Ambassadors' Batch #1 Timeline.....	41
Table 13 Ambassadors' Batch #2 Timeline.....	41
Table 14 Ambassadors' Batch #3 Timeline.....	42
Table 15 Example of the disclaimer for COcyber publications.....	42

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EITD	EIT DIGITAL, COcyber coordinator leading project management (WP1) and synergies (WP6).
EOS	The European Organisation for Security, COcyber partner leading Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres (WP2).
LC	The Lisbon Council, COcyber partner leading Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform (WP3).
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
AUS	AUSTRALO marketing lab, COcyber partner leading communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement (WP5).
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
WP	Work Package, form the COcyber working process.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator serves to measure the status and success of the communication and dissemination activities.

Executive Summary

This report defines the overall strategy for the outreach and impact management of the COcyber project, delivering the research results to the stakeholders and paving the way for sustainable implementation of results beyond the project. This master strategy consists of four key areas:

Communication is the first one of the four building blocks of this framework. It means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the COcyber project and its results to target audiences, including cybersecurity professionals, entrepreneurs, decision-makers, relevant media, and the public and engaging in a two-way exchange. With proactive communication campaigns and a mixed communication portfolio, the COcyber project enables to foster the exchange of information and to endorse collaborations of civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders.

Dissemination is the second element to sustain the project's impact. Our dissemination strategy will plan and organise the publication of the public project results, including primarily scientific publications in open access, public deliverables, and participation to scientific and non-scientific events to spread the research results. The objective is to enable the target stakeholders to make use of the produced project results.

Ambassador Programme is the third building block to the strategy; The COcyber project will assemble a pool of individuals (e.g., ambassadors) with a solid online presence (active on social media, high number of followers) and a reputation in the cybersecurity sector. The recruited ambassadors will support maximising the outreach of the project towards the targeted stakeholders, and hence contribute to fostering the communication and dissemination activities.

Exploitation is the fourth cornerstone of this framework ensuring that the project results are used beyond the project duration, in a sustainable manner. This report presents the key principles for the exploitation and sustainability plans of COcyber, which will be further developed under dedicated tasks in Work Package 6.

Introduction

This report is part of the COcyber Work Package 5 “Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement”. The main aim of WP5 is to design and execute the most effective measures to maximise the impact of COcyber, promote widely the activities and results of the project, make them accessible to the cybersecurity ecosystem, and foster their use and replication. The specific objectives are to:

- **Implement comprehensive dissemination and communication strategies** that will well position the project, increase the visibility of activities and the adoption of the results at the EU and national levels.
- **Develop a strong brand for the COcyber project** and design attractive marketing collaterals and promotional material to support the initiative.
- Coordinate the participation in and organisation of **large-scale project promotional events** for all stakeholder groups.
- **Identify and engage with key experts and decision-makers** from the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres to create an Ambassador Programme with the aim to deepen and amplify the COcyber outreach and engagement efforts at local, European, and international levels.

In this sense, this report provides a strategy to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders. It outlines the target groups and their segments, presents key messages, tools and channels used, as well as the ambassador programme methodology.

1.1 Structure of the report

The report consists of five sections, but all the treated topics are interrelated, each of them contributing to foster the impact and sustainability of the COcyber project:

- **Section 2** introduces the COcyber stakeholders defining their profiles and the key engagement tactics. These groups are the target audience of the project’s communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies.
- **Section 3** lays out the specific plans for the COcyber communication and dissemination. These will guide the activities throughout the project, but, at the same time, they can be refined and adjusted based on the research progress and identified needs or opportunities.
- **Section 4** presents the project’s exploitation principles, while laying the foundation for the sustainability of the achieved key exploitable results.
- **Section 5** shares the conclusions and the next steps for the impact activities of the project.

1.2 Related tasks and deliverables

This deliverable offering an overarching strategy for COcyber dissemination, communication and exploitation is published as a part of the WP5 tasks:

- T5.1 Dissemination and communication strategy and activities
- T5.2 COcyber branding and promotional assets
- T5.3 Project promotional events
- T5.4 COcyber stakeholder engagement and Ambassador Programme

In line with these tasks, the report will impact the forthcoming deliverables under work package 5, which are:

- D5.1 COcyber Hackathon (M11, EITD):
- D5.3 Dissemination and communication activities performance reports- v1 (M12, AUS)
- D5.4 Dissemination and communication activities performance reports- v2 (M24, AUS)
- D5.5 Project final conference (M24, EITD)

In addition, this report is closely linked to all other work packages and tasks, as it aims to provide concrete tools and channels to communicate and disseminate all crucial COcyber project activities and achievements to the target stakeholders. The collaboration among WP5 and WP6 *"Synergies with existing initiatives, exploitation, and sustainability"* will be especially close since the latter is dedicated to ensuring proper exploitation of the COcyber results and outputs during and after the project ends, prepare for the long-term sustainability of the achieved results, and foster and achieve synergies with relevant cybersecurity existing initiatives.

Finally, the WP2 *"Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres"*, and especially task 2.1 *"COcyber Secretariat & governance"* contribute to refining the COcyber stakeholder groups that are at the core of all project activities, and therefore, crucial to this report.

2 COcyber Stakeholders

The project has defined the target stakeholder groups to whom the COcyber outreach activities are addressed to, and the principal objectives are to raise awareness about the project activities and results, to make them use the project results that are in open access, and finally to define how they can exploit the project results in a sustainable manner even beyond the project.

2.1 Definition of the target stakeholders

The COcyber activities are targeted at all key stakeholders acting in the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres, and these groups are defined in Figure 1. The target stakeholders are beneficiaries of COcyber communication and dissemination activities, and the project aims to involve them proactively in the organised public consultation, events, workshops, seminars, and round-table discussions etc. (especially under WP4 “Know-how, good practice sharing and information transfer activities”).

Figure 1 COcyber Stakeholder Groups

Next to these target stakeholder groups, COcyber works with an **advisory board** composed of high-level experts in cybersecurity-related organisations feeding into the different project activities. Their involvement is coordinated within the work package 1 Project management and quality assurance.

Moreover, Deliverable 2.1 COcyber governance and management plan¹ defines the COcyber community formed by these different stakeholder groups and provides a

¹ (delivered in December 2024 (M6), main author: EOS, publication level: sensitive (SEN))

complete understanding of how the different target stakeholders can, on one side, benefit from the COcyber Community and the other side, contribute and add value to it.

2.2 Stakeholder Engagement Tactics

The COcyber team will scout and contact relevant European stakeholders, initiatives, and projects in cybersecurity civil and defence spheres that could be interested in two-way collaboration. The aim is to create opportunities to exchange information, knowledge, and best practices, develop synergies for stakeholder events and produce awareness publications. **The objective is to gather a minimum of 2000 unique contact points** for the project's stakeholder's database who could be approached with an individual email campaign.

The proactive stakeholder engagement will be carried out throughout the project in different channels, including notably:

- **Partners networks** – the trusted and relevant contacts from the partner organisations networks. The COcyber team² is formed by a group of five organisations that are actively involved in the European **cybersecurity** and digital transformation arena. For instance:
 - **EIT Digital's** (EITD) ecosystem features 300+ partners driving the European digital innovation.
 - **European Organisation for Security** (EOS) members are based in 15 EU countries and organised in different working groups.
 - **The Lisbon Council** (LC), as a think-thank, is rooted in the European and national public policy bodies.
 - **Solvay Business School of Economics and Management** (SBS-EM, ULB) is part of Université Libre de Brussels, and its members host expert positions in international institutions such as the European Security and Defence College or Belgian Cybersecurity Coalition.
 - **AUSTRALO** (AUS) participates to several EU innovation networks, such as Next Generation Internet, Big Data Value Association, European Business Network.
- **Active European institutions and organisations in the cybersecurity landscape.** These include structures such as EC DG CNECT, European Defence Agency (EDA), European Defence Fund (EDF), European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC), European Cybersecurity Organisation (ECISO), EU Cyber Direct, and ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity).
- **Relevant national strategies and European cybersecurity projects** funded under the Horizon Europe programme, Digital Europe programme, European Defence Fund.

² <https://cocyber.eu/team>

- o Especially, the sibling project, ECYBRIDGE³, was funded under the same call (DIGITAL-ECCC-2023-DEPLOY-CYBER-04), and the collaboration with this project has already started with several meetings and a key stakeholder event⁴.
- o Running European project clusters in the fields of defence and cybersecurity, such as the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECI)⁵ and the SecureCyber Cluster⁶ will be leveraged.

In addition to the partners’ work in involving stakeholders in the COcyber community, the project establishes **an ambassador programme** recruiting **individual cybersecurity experts** who support the COcyber’s stakeholder engagement and dissemination activities. The full ambition and strategy of the ambassador programme are presented in Section 4.

Finally, Table 1 provides a more detailed description of each major target stakeholder group the main benefits of the project for the group and the key tactics for their engagement.

Table 1 Main benefits by major target group

Target Group	Main benefits for the group
Cybersecurity professionals Experts working in public or private organisations and disposing a key role in cybersecurity topics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New collaborations and business opportunities, resulting in diversified revenue streams, access to valuable insights and expertise. • Enhanced ability to respond to cross-sectorial cyber incidents, influence project initiatives for effectively addressing evolving cyber threats.
National, regional, and local authorities and agencies for cybersecurity e.g., National Cybersecurity Coordination Centres (NCCC), Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs), Cyber Emergency Response Teams (CERTs), Law Enforcement Agencies, Ministries of Defence, Foreign Affairs, Digitalisation/Telecommunications, Armed Forces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased capacity for informed policy decisions through access to expert insights and research; increased resilience against cross-border cyberattacks through harmonised practices; • Improved communication and coordination with relevant stakeholders; enhanced public-private partnerships and active involvement; • Fostering a sense of shared responsibility for national, regional, and local cybersecurity; • Enhanced ability to respond to cross-sectorial cyber incidents, influence project initiatives for effectively addressing evolving cyber threats, and shape the development of the COcyber Platform, ensuring it addresses specific information-sharing and coordination requirements.
Private sector including e.g., Operators of critical infrastructures, Information Sharing and Analysis Centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New collaborations and business opportunities, resulting in diversified revenue streams, access to valuable insights and expertise;

³ <https://ecybridge.eu/>

⁴ <https://cocyber.eu/events/navigating-cyber-storms-civilian-and-defence-synergy-digitalised-world>

⁵ <https://www.finsec-project.eu/ecsci>

⁶ <https://spatial-h2020.eu/spatial-joins-the-securecyber-cluster/>

<p>(ISACs), Digital service providers, Cybersecurity companies, Defence/military contractors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved competitive positioning, leveraging the project's network for mutual benefit; • Collaboration progress between industrial sectors, promoting cross-sectorial innovation to foster a sense of shared responsibility for the project's success, and active involvement drives advancements in product and service offerings; • Able to address specific industry collaboration challenges effectively, collaborate with other industrial stakeholders to explore joint ventures and innovative solutions, leveraging the project's network, and promote the project's recommendations within industry associations and networks, enhancing its credibility and reach.
<p>Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), startups e.g., local SMEs and start-ups</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boosted opportunities for collaboration and innovation with the COcyber consortium, resulting in competitive advantages, access to shared knowledge and expertise, reducing the cost of cybersecurity solutions, and enhanced ability to tap into emerging dual-use technologies; • Able to shape project initiatives to address industry-specific innovation challenges effectively, collaborate with COcyber project stakeholders to develop dual-use technologies and solutions, meeting both cybersecurity civilians and defence sector requirements, and collaborate with the COcyber project on capacity building activities, nurturing a highly skilled cybersecurity workforce to meet industry demands.
<p>Academic and Research Institutions, Innovation centres, and Training providers e.g., Cybersecurity research and innovation centres, European Innovation Council (EIC), Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) specialised in cybersecurity, European Security & Defence College (ESDC), Defence Academies, Defence Research and Innovation centres</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased collaboration with relevant cybersecurity actors on cutting-edge cybersecurity research, fostering academic excellence, and opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, leading to innovative breakthroughs; • Enhanced capacity for producing research with practical applications, increased exposure and collaboration opportunities within the cybersecurity community, and encouragement for scholars to pursue careers in cybersecurity, addressing skill gaps; • Opportunities to influence the COcyber project's research agenda, ensuring it aligns with emerging trends and challenges, and shape research directions, steering them towards emerging challenges and technological advancements.

3 Communication and Dissemination Plan

Communication and dissemination are the two major elements of reinforcing the COcyber project’s impact. The Communication strategy focuses on building a brand identity and raising awareness about the project whereas the dissemination strategy is dedicated to ensuring that the stakeholders can make use of the project results. Both activities are complementary and run throughout the project (from M1 until M24).

3.1 Communication Strategy

COcyber implements a solid communication plan that is versatile and agile. Therefore, the project has adopted a **funnelled approach** (see Figure 2) ensuring targeted but wide communication towards all possible target stakeholders. Such an approach primarily focuses on generating awareness by conveying key aspects and benefits of the project to all target audiences and end users.

Figure 2 COcyber's communication funnel

Firstly, visual material that is easy to interpret, understand and recognise will be designed and communicated, which will allow COcyber concepts and benefits to become instantly identifiable to the broader audience while growing and cultivating further interest towards the project and its key outcomes.

Secondly, additional customised content will be produced and communicated towards specialised target group audiences aiming at creating and maintaining information that will be extracted from project deliverables, meetings and discussions with partners, public consultations and all involved knowledge exchange events. These will be relayed through the COcyber communication channels to further support active user engagement and consolidation of the COcyber ecosystem.

3.1.1 Objectives

A set of objectives has been defined to drive the communication plan, and these are crucial for implementing the plan throughout the project. The general overall objectives are to:

- **Increase awareness and interest** in the project for building a sustainable ecosystem for future expansion.
- **Communicate results and shared knowledge** to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- **Deliver top-level messages** about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- **Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences** about COcyber to the widest possible community.

Although communication objectives are aggregated, some of these objectives are being related to specific target groups only and will be approached with specific tools and activities throughout the lifespan of the project (see Table 2).

Table 2 Communication objectives per target group

	Awareness about & interest in	Communicate technical & scientific results	Deliver top-level messages	Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences
Cybersecurity professionals	✓	✓	✓	
National, regional and local authorities for cybersecurity	✓	✓	✓	
European institutions and agencies for cybersecurity, defence and diplomacy	✓	✓	✓	
Regulatory authorities and standardisation bodies	✓	✓	✓	
SMEs and Start-Ups	✓	✓		
Private sector actors	✓	✓		

Academic and Research institutions, Innovation centres	✓	✓	✓	
European projects and national initiatives for cybersecurity and defence	✓	✓	✓	
General public	✓			✓

More importantly, COcyber has fixed itself a list of key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be monitored throughout the projects. These enable us to ensure that the communication plan is on track and manage all possible risks in an agile manner. Table 3 lists these communication KPIs, and there the baseline value refers to the minimum requirements to be achieved by the project, whereas the target value refers to the most optimistic value to be reached by project activities.

Table 3 KPIs for Communication

Activity	Definition of the indicator	Baseline value	Target value
COcyber Platform	Monthly visitors on the COcyber platform	400	500
Success stories	no. projects featured		12
Social media	No. followers across project social media channels	1500	2000
	<i>No. of monthly impression</i>		1500
PRs	Press releases	4	4
	External media articles (earned)		8
Email campaigns	Total leads in the stakeholder’s database		2000
Newsletters	No. of published newsletters		8
	Featuring in external newsletters		6
Podcasts	No. of produced episodes		6
Branding & Graphical Material	No. graphical elements designed		30
Slide Decks & Working Material	No. slide decks and working material		6
Multimedia Material	multimedia elements		10

3.1.2 Communication phases

The communication activities are planned in three phases that are in accordance with the project span, in line with the key activities from the other work packages.

cocyper Communication Phases

Figure 3 Communication in three phases

Phase 1 – Plan and adjust | (M1 – M6) (July 2024 – December 2024)

The first communication phase started in M1 of the project and it's arriving to its end (now in M6). It primarily aimed at planning all activities, setting up the main communication tools and channels (Website, social media), and identifying potential target groups and stakeholders. However, the latter is an activity that will be implemented throughout the whole project. This first phase also included the concept of adjusting the plan: whenever this is required, the communication plan will be revisited and adjusted according to the needs or circumstances that may exist at a specific period of time. During this phase, initial communication activities (i.e. press releases, release of newsletters and promo material) also took place. The adjustments to the communication plan will be made in an agile manner throughout the project based on the achievements and stakeholders' requirements.

Phase 2 – Early Bird Communication | (M7 – M12) (January 2025– June 2025)

During this phase early bird communication activities aim to raise awareness of a wider public and to specific communities, about the project and its forthcoming activities and actions. Emphasis will be given to the online tools and measures, especially content production on the COcyber platform and on social media, as they tend to have a wider reach than traditional measures. During this phase, participation for networking purposes to webinars or other online events, articles over the internet about the project (by leveraging the established synergies.) will take place. This phase will last for the whole duration of the project as it mainly focuses on communicating the generic aspect of the project to a wide stakeholder base.

Phase 3 – Targeted Communication | (M13 – M24) (July 2025– June 2026)

The third communication phase requires the project to be in the relative maturity stage while an increasing number of tangible outcomes are released. During this phase, targeted communication activities will take place, such as publishing articles, blogs, or posts about certain project outcomes and benefits, hosting and/or participating in relevant external stakeholder events, producing targeted communication material (i.e. videos) for the community, etc. This phase will run in parallel with phase 2 as it focuses on targeted communication actions for specific audiences and not actions for the whole community.

3.1.3 Measures

To achieve the fixed objectives, the COcyber project will deploy a wide range of targeted communications towards its target groups. These activities are framed with the project branding and an editorial plan.

3.1.3.1 COcyber visual identity and branding

The “**COcyber Brand book**”⁷ sets up the branding strategy of the project and the visual tools for implementing it. COcyber’s visual identity includes the defined logo, the colour scheme, an image bank and the fonts.

Figure 4 COcyber Brand book Cover

In all created project material, the guideline is to use the following:

- The title text: **DM Sans Bold**
- The body text: DM Sans Regular
- The defined colour scheme (see Figure 5)

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/12819151>

Figure 5 COcyber Colours Scheme

Moreover, the initial **COcyber branding kit** includes the following essential visual elements: **the logo and digital banners, a roll-up a banner, a flyer, and a common email signature.**

The project logo is a crucial part of the visual identity. The created logo, including its different digital formats (see Figure 6), was shared with partners at the start of the project. **The banners** (see Figure 7) are used essentially on the project’s social media pages to align them with the project identity.

Figure 6 COcyber Logo formats

Figure 7 COcyber Header Banner

The **roll-up banner**⁸ is used for engaging stakeholders' attention to the project in key events and exhibitions.

Figure 8 COcyber Roll-Up Banner

The **project flyer**⁹ can be used for engaging with stakeholders, for instance while recruiting them to the project's public consultations. We aim to reduce the paper prints, for environmental reasons, and encourage partners to use the digital version of the flyer as much as possible.

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/14098002>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14097577>

Figure 9 COcyber marketing flyer

Finally, the **COcyber email signature** is a visual tool for partners to use in one-to-one mailing campaigns with the target stakeholders.

Recipients

[COcyber] Example

Dear COcyber Community,

I am happy to share with you our next key event this week hosted by our sister project, the ECYBridge: <https://cocyper.eu/events>

With kind regards,
Mona Marill

Figure 10 COcyber email signature

In addition, AUS will produce different visual materials throughout the project based on the needs and running communication campaigns.

3.1.3.2 Key language elements

AUS leads the communication of the project; however, all partners contribute to it to reach different audiences from all EU countries and beyond. Therefore, it is important to set the common basis for the communication language elements.

The cornerstones of the COcyber related communications are the following aspects:

- COcyber is a European initiative, collaborative effort, coordination and support action, building a proactive ecosystem of key stakeholders in cybersecurity and defence areas. Hence, its attitude is **encouraging, diplomatic and inclusive**.
- **The tone of voice:** deployed throughout the communication and dissemination, is positive, approachable, and informative.
- **Grammar:** The project work language is English; all partners should communicate by following the spelling and grammar of British English.
- **Partners names:** In all public communication, refer to partners with their complete names and add the abbreviation in parentheses after the name.
- **Project abbreviation:** The correct spelling is COcyber, referring to the project name "Coordination between the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres.

3.1.3.3 Templates

The partners use dedicated templates in all COcyber-related communications and reporting. Several internal templates have been created and shared with the consortium, including:

- **Deliverable template** that is used for all official project deliverables to be submitted as a part of the project monitoring to the European Commission.
- **Slide-deck template** that can be used in preparing presentations in both, internal project meetings and external stakeholder meetings and events.
- **Document template** that can be used for creating various project related documents (e.g., meeting agendas and minutes, etc.).

3.1.3.4 Mixed promotion portfolio

The COcyber project designs and deploys a mixed portfolio of communication actions to reach as wide array as possible of the different stakeholders. The results of each communication campaign will be monitored and assessed to fine-tune the strategies and activities throughout the project.

Table 4 lists the different set of tools created and used for the project communication.

Table 4 COcyber communication tools

Tool	Objective	Channel	Target Group
COcyber platform	This online platform (see) is a key instrument for enhancing visibility of the project, informing visitors about the project concept. All public project results (deliverables, publications, articles, and news) are published on the website to allow all interested parties to learn about the project activities and results. Moreover, the platform will become a central hub for information, resources, and coordination tools that will empower stakeholders to work together on shared cybersecurity goals	https://coccyber.eu/	All
COcyber Contact Mail	External stakeholders can contact the project team directly for any further information about the project or collaboration proposition. AUS and EITD oversee these contacts and re-direct to the relevant partners.	contact@coccyber.eu	All
Partners' website sites	The project will work with the marketing teams with each partner organisation to feature the key project information to their website and hence do web cross-referencing.	www.eitdigital.eu www.eos-eu.com lisboncouncil.net sbsem.ulb.be www.australo.org	All
Social media	We will share project updates and results several times a week to reach our target audiences quickly and with a minimal cost. COcyber is present in LinkedIn (the privileged social media channel), BlueSky, and YouTube. More channels can be joined according to the raising needs.	LinkedIn @coccyber BlueSky @coccyber YouTube @coccyber	All
Newsletters	These will be published every four months presenting the latest project updates and results, as well as news from community members. The newsletter will be sent to its subscribers via LinkedIn where it has an established community of followers. In addition, the project aims to feature in related external stakeholders' newsletters.	Via LinkedIn Newsletter tool and related external newsletters.	All
Press Releases	These are issued at each important project milestone (such as the release of a new public consultation) to inform online and offline press, media and journalists about the project and to gain external media articles about the project.	A PDF document, published on the project website and Zenodo ¹⁰ , and on partners' networks.	Media, journalists, scientific community, policy makers & authorities
Slide-decks and one-pagers	These can be used for one-to-one engagement (e-mails and meetings) with stakeholders to mark as an entry point to the project.	A PDF document, published on the project website and on Zenodo.	Industry, end-users, SMEs, scientific community, policy makers & authorities
General spreading	Creating and publishing COcyber related articles in different online media targets and shaping a	Publications in external online	All

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/coccyber/>

	communication globe around the web sphere to maximise the outreach of scope to all stakeholders.	platforms and websites.	
Printed material	Most of the PR material will be available as e-documents and printing will occur as required (e.g. for events, workshops, etc.). Based on specific needs in the project, we will also explore other innovative alternatives to traditional informative material.	Creation of dedicated PDF flyer, slide-deck and a roll-up banner.	All
Podcasts and videos	Audiovisual content is proven to be efficient and complementary to publications, articles, and reports. It helps to broaden the outreach and target new audiences. COcyber will produce a podcast series with short episodes presenting the project's essence and multiple dynamic short videos that foster our presence in the social media.	Creation and editing of video and audio material distributed through the website and social media.	All

Figure 11 A glimpse of the COcyber platform

The first tools for the COcyber communication are already available, notably:

- **Social media accounts**, in LinkedIn, and X, now changed into BlueSky, are running since July 2024. These accounts follow a weekly social media plan established by AUS.
- **The project platform cocyper.eu** is up and running since September 2024. New release with more functionalities for knowledge sharing will be done in December 2024.

- **New content** is published monthly on the website’s “Updates” page related to news¹¹ and events¹².
- **The promo material kit** (defined earlier in this section) is designed and available.

3.1.3.5 Editorial Plan

One of the main activities to focus on during the first year is the publication of original content under the “news” and “events”–sections of the coccyber.eu website. The objective is to publish at least two blog articles each month. These knowledge publications will help reach an increasing number of visitors through the project platform.

To make the interest of our community consistently high, we plan to diversify the content of the pieces, regrouping the content in the following series:

- **WHAT IS COcyber?** This series introduces the project to specialised and non-specialised audiences. The task is to divide detailed information such as the objectives, methodology, challenges, and impacts into a series of articles.
- **MEET THE TEAM BEHIND COcyber** – This series can be paired with a social media campaign highlighting the consortium’s partners through interviews with a member/team of experts on the project. The purpose is to communicate their experience, work within the project and importance to achieve COcyber’s objectives.
- **JOIN THE COcyber ECOSYSTEM**—This series promotes the initiative’s added value and benefits for related third parties, encouraging them to join the community. It also includes an expression of interest campaign for potential ambassadors.
- **GET TO KNOW COcyber’s ECOSYSTEM**—This series can be paired with a social media campaign spotlighting the ambassadors and members of the ecosystem through interviews, showcasing the experience and knowledge they bring to the community.
- **ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION** – To engage with stakeholders, blog articles will be created to promote the events, activities and workshops where the COcyber community participates. This content includes quotes from the team behind COcyber and its ecosystem, showcasing their learnings and experiences.
- **WHAT WE ACHIEVED** – This series highlights the project’s milestones and achievements throughout its duration, concluding with final results from different perspectives.

¹¹ <https://coccyber.eu/news>

¹² <https://coccyber.eu/events>

Moreover, all series will be paired with dedicated social media campaigns. In Annex 1, one can find an overview of the editorial plan for the first year, and it will be continuously fine-tuned according to the ongoing activities and results.

3.2 Dissemination Strategy

The dissemination strategy, closely tied to the communication strategy, aims to ensure methods, tools and channels for the general uptake of the COcyber results, even beyond the project's lifetime. The project aims to foster the active and two-way exchange of knowledge and information among the cybersecurity civil and defence communities. The grant agreement defined the dissemination goals, and their progress will be assessed throughout the project.

3.2.1 Objectives

The dissemination objectives have been defined since the beginning of the project. These are closely interlinked both with communication objectives and with the overall project objectives, all to create an impact beyond the boundaries of this project. To resume, our dissemination activities aim to:

- **Facilitate the exchange of know-how, knowledge and information** among the target stakeholders.
- **Share the project results** to the widest possible community, building a cluster around the project. This is supported essentially by the COcyber secretary (under task 2.1) and the establishment of synergies with other relevant initiatives (under task 6.1).
- Enable external stakeholders to use **all public results** (e.g., scientific publications, technical webinars, public deliverables, policy recommendations, etc.) **in open access**.
- Endorse the COcyber team participation in **scientific, technical and networking events** to foster proactive stakeholder engagement.
- **Raise the visibility** of the COcyber activities and results among the identified stakeholders.

The project has fixed itself a list of key performance indicators (KPIs) for dissemination, enabling to monitor and assess its success (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). In this table, the baseline value refers to the minimum requirements to be achieved by the project, whereas the target value refers to the most optimistic value to be reached by project activities.

Table 5 COcyber KPIs for Dissemination

Activity	Definition	Baseline value	Target value
Awareness Publications	Awareness publications, including articles, blog posts, testimonials, and factsheets.		50
	<i>Number of impressions</i>		200,000
Scientific publications	Number of research paper produced	2	4
Project documentation	Project documents (downloads)		1000
Portals	no. 3rd-party portals with engagement:	5	5
Events	3rd-party relevant events participated		15
	no. of people reached through online/on-site events		3000
Ambassador Programme	high-level profiles engaged under the Ambassador Programme	15	27
Community Efforts	active collaborations implemented with other relevant initiatives and projects		20

3.2.2 Dissemination phases

Like the communication plan, the dissemination plan will be implemented in three different phases, as shown in Figure 12. These phases aim to support the coordination and prioritisation of the dissemination activities in line with the project’s timeline.

Figure 12 COcyber dissemination phases

Phase 1 Identify and analyse | (M1-M6) (July 2024 – December 2024)

During this phase, running now, the project’s framework is analysed to be aligned with the dissemination plan. Moreover, the focus is on identifying internal and external barriers and obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities, as well as on defining the priorities and actions for the first year of the project. During this phase, the scouting, identification and contacting key stakeholders starts from this phase onwards. Also, mapping the major stakeholder events is done to ensure that these are on the project’s radar. In addition, the first awareness articles are published on the COcyber platform. This phase is also dedicated to setting up the strategy for the ambassador programme, that will foster the dissemination.

Phase 2 Outreach and Influence | (M7-M12) (January – June 2025)

The main objective of the second phase is to increase the impact and awareness around COcyber, and to share the first achievements and activities of the project. All channels (including communication) will be adapted to the specific needs of this phase, and to properly find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project’s results. Participation in events, as well as organisation of a hackathon, round table discussions, workshops, webinars, podcasts etc., will boost the dissemination process. Based on different event participation and engaged collaborations, specific PR material will also be produced. In this phase, the appointed ambassadors start collaboration with the project, with the aim to leverage their networks in building the COcyber community and spreading the project’s activities and outcomes.

Phase 3 Embrace and Amplify | (M13 -M24) (July 2025 – June 2026)

This phase will leverage the general awareness raised by the two initial phases, attracting more potential end users and clientele interested in COcyber. Earlier phases will be evaluated and, if needed, priorities, measures and dissemination channels will be refined. Participation in events, workshops, and conferences as well as paper and publication production will be increased. This period will be concluded by a final conference organised by the project to share the key achievements with the community.

3.2.3 Measures

As already highlighted, communication and dissemination are closely interlinked; therefore, several tools are common for both. However, there are some tools specific to the dissemination and to create impact for the project, and these are detailed in Table 6.

Table 6 COcyber's measures for dissemination

Tool	Objective	Channel	Target Group
Events	The essential part of the stakeholder engagement takes places in varied events where it is possible to present the project to widen audiences and to directly connect with professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meetings - Seminars - Training sessions - Workshops - Exhibitions 	- All

	from different stakeholder organisations. COcyber will join at least 15 external events as well as host a hackathon and a final event for the project.	- Conferences	
Ambassador Programme	Between 15 and 27 European professionals are recruited to support the project in its communication and dissemination activities boosting the community creation and management. The entire strategy is described in Section 4.	- Online communication tools. - Events. - The COcyber platform	- All
Synergies with related initiatives	Under WP6, the project focuses on establishing synergies with existing related initiatives funded by Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programme. This enables to leverage both the established communities reaching a wider audience and the relevant ongoing work on the cybersecurity sector.	- Cross-communication - One-to-one meetings - Workshops - The COcyber platform	- All
Project documentation	All public deliverables will be shared in open access via our public repository, and through our communication channels.	- Project website ¹³ - Zenodo - Social media channels	- All
Awareness publications	These targeted articles can disseminate the outcomes to a wider target audience. The project will publish and contribute to blogs and articles to foster knowledge sharing across the cybersecurity communities.	- Project website - External websites - Newsletters - Media outlets	- All
Open access library	COcyber will provide open access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, and other research papers by using Zenodo online repository, where it is possible to deposit both publications and data, while providing a direct online link to them.	- Zenodo ¹⁴	- All
Research papers	The project aims to publish and contribute to four research papers based on the gathered data and relevant to civilian and defence cybersecurity. One of our main objectives is to ensure the technical achievements and experimental findings of the project will be known and exploited by a larger research	- Scientific Conferences - Scientific articles - Books	- Academic stakeholders in the community. - Public authorities for cybersecurity

¹³ <https://cocyber.eu/publications>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/cocyber/>

	community and related scientific domains. These will be in open access.		- Related research initiatives.
Exchange of know-how and information-sharing activities	Under WP4, the project will organise different activities to facilitate the exchange of know-how among the cybersecurity communities. These allow direct engagement with the target stakeholders on focused key topics. The format of these activities will be roundtables, public consultations, workshops and seminars.	- Academic cursus of the scientific project partners	- All
The EC Services for projects	COcyber will monitor and assess opportunities that the European Commission proposes for the RIA projects, as their support can endorse the dissemination of the project's impact.	- Horizon Magazine - Horizon Results Platform - Innovation radar - CORDIS	- Scientific community and research projects - Policy makers and authorities
Stakeholder Feedback	Collecting feedback from the project's stakeholders enables to expand its horizon, especially in terms of sustainability of the results, but also spread the outcomes to a specialized audience. This can also support the decision making in critical issues and to refine the project's strategies.	- Online surveys and polls via cocyper.eu	- Public authorities for cybersecurity. - SMEs and Start-Ups - Private sector actors. - Policy makers and authorities - Scientific community and research projects

3.3 Activity Monitoring and Risk Mitigation

Monitoring and adjusting the communication and dissemination plans, on a frequent basis, is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given on the pre-assessment of information needs, on the monitoring frequency (on monthly basis) and the method of collecting evidence.

3.3.1 Monitoring strategy

The execution and effectiveness of the Communication & Dissemination plan is dependent on close monitoring, and a flexible and prompt response mechanism. Every designed and implemented activity will be monitored and evaluated according to its impact and closely related to the KPIs.

Figure 13 Communication and dissemination cycle

- **Design:** Design each activity based on the communication and dissemination plans and the desired impact.
- **Execute:** Execute according to plan.
- **Monitor:** Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results. Monitoring will be based on a template that is available only to partners through an internal monitoring tool.
- **Evaluate:** Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase.
- **Learn:** Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it.
- **Adjust:** Absorb findings and lessons learnt, and adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

All outcomes and results of the Communication & Dissemination Plan will be reported in D5.3 Dissemination and communication performance reports v1 in M12 and D5.4 Dissemination and communication performance reports v2 in M24.

3.3.2 Possible Risks

There are several risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project. These risks will be monitored and mitigated by the Communication & Dissemination leader who will also control these risks on a regular basis and will report any changes to the Project Coordinator. Examples of communication risks include but are not limited to:

Table 7 Dissemination & Communication Risks

Risk	Measure to minimise Risk
<p>Inadequate stakeholder engagement: Failure to engage effectively with stakeholders could result in a lack of support, participation, or buy-in for the project, which could hinder its success.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact: High • Likelihood: Low 	<p>These C&D plans are crucial for the stakeholder engagement. COcyber continuously communicates with stakeholders to keep them informed and involved throughout the project. All engagement activities will be planned with clear objectives and outcomes in mind to ensure a positive engagement result for attendees and avoid overlaps. Moreover, the scouts, maps and contacts continuously the target stakeholders to facilitate engagement and outreach.</p>
<p>Lack of interest or uptake from target audiences: If the project outputs are not of interest or relevant to its target audiences, it could affect the impact and overall success of the project (for example lack of interest by national authorities to collaborate on the COcyber Platform).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact: High • Likelihood: Medium 	<p>The Project Director with the support and overall advice of the Advisory Board will gather regular market insights to ensure that the project outputs are meeting the needs of the target audiences and adjust the project plan as necessary to ensure relevance and uptake. In addition, the COcyber Ambassador network will be leveraged to ensure proper uptake of the project outputs and results by all stakeholders.</p>
<p>Lack of cross-sectoral representation. There are certain key stakeholder groups, particularly from less represented sectors who may not be adequately involved in knowledge-sharing activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact: Medium • Likelihood: Medium 	<p>To address this risk, the partners will ensure to tailor content to the needs and interests of the whole range of stakeholders involved, while also employing diverse and interactive dissemination methods. Moreover, regular stakeholders feedback, gathered during the project's meetings and events, will be collected to assess and improve the effectiveness of knowledge-sharing activities.</p>
<p>Language and cultural barriers. The project involves multiple partners from different countries, which could result in cultural barriers and different approaches that could impact communication and collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact: Low • Likelihood: Low 	<p>The WP Communication Leader (AUS), in coordination with the Project Director at EITD will establish communication protocols, especially tools and process for internal communication, and, if necessary, provide support to team members to ensure effective cross-cultural communication and collaboration.</p>

4 COcyber Ambassador Programme Strategy

Task 5.4 “COcyber stakeholder engagement and Ambassador Programme” identifies and assesses the target stakeholders with the capacity to reinforce the width and depth of the knowledge transfer efforts (T4.2), outreach activities (T5.1) and synergies (T6.1) carried out by the project. The main result of the activity will be the COcyber ‘Ambassador Programme’ – a network of high-level and trusted individual experts, policymakers, and decision-makers in the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres recruited and empowered to advocate for the project and its community. The COcyber project ambition is to recruit ambassadors across the 27 Member States to ensure regional, national, and EU-wide impact in terms of the project’s dissemination and stakeholder engagement. This impact will essentially directly endorse the dissemination and communication key performance indicators defined in Sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.1.

4.1 Overview of the objectives

The COcyber project will assemble a pool of individuals (ambassadors) with **a solid online presence** (active on social media, high number of followers) and a **reputation in the cybersecurity sector**. They will support maximising the outreach of the project towards the target stakeholders, and hence contribute to fostering the communication and dissemination activities.

Our ambassadors will:

- **Create and share quality content** related to civilian and defence cybersecurity topics.
- **Increase COcyber’s visibility** on different communication channels (social media and websites).
- **Speak about the COcyber at relevant events** and with local, national and European media.
- **Be kept informed** so they can communicate about the latest developments and impacts of the COcyber programme.
- **Provide their insights and feedback** to support further improvements to the COcyber ecosystem.

A network of **high-level and trusted individual experts, policymakers, and decision-makers** in the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres recruited and empowered to advocate for the project and its community. The recruitment is done through an internal scouting process, in which all COcyber partners suggest the most relevant potential candidates from their networks. The consortium rates the candidates for each batch recruitment round, and the top candidates are contacted to offer the position. All selected ambassadors will settle a contract with EITD to frame this collaboration, and they will work with COcyber for six months, under the supervision of AUS, as illustrated in Figure 14.

COcyber Ambassadors' Journey

Figure 14 COcyber Ambassador's Journey

Depending on the level of commitment, the project can **provide economic compensation for their services**.

4.2 Ambassador Programme Structure

We will implement the programme with an agile methodology that can be adjusted as the COcyber project evolves. This approach enables the Ambassador Programme to run quickly, considering the continuous evolution of the project's activities and needs in stakeholder engagement and community building.

The central aim of the ambassador programme is to **maximise the outreach of the project's activities and results**. Therefore, we will recruit **high-level professionals** from the European cybersecurity arena. The ambassador programme's functioning will be piloted under Batch 1, and it will follow **a smooth process with minimum administrative efforts** required from the high-level participants (who often lack availability for meetings, reporting, etc.).

4.2.1 Three batches of Ambassadorships

The ambassador programme will be **structured in 3 different batches of 6 months each**. For each batch a preliminary list with 10-15 candidates will be proposed to a Selection Committee formed by consortium members, and 5-9 ambassadors will be recruited according to criteria such as geographical diversity, online presence, and type of stakeholder.

Structuring the programme in three batches enables the ambassador programme to be **agile and to respond to the evolution and progress** of the COcyber project’s activities. For instance, **the first batch** of ambassadors starts running during the second half of the first project year, and therefore the **focus will be on enlarging the stakeholder’s community**. The **next two batches** will focus more on **disseminating the achievements** towards the target stakeholders.

Figure 15 resumes the timeline for each batch covering all ambassador programme phases: scouting, evaluation of candidates, contracting the selected professionals, ambassadors’ active involvement to COcyber and finalisation of the ambassadorship. Based on the pilot round (Batch#1), the timelines can still evolve according to the best fit for the project.

Figure 15 Ambassador Programme Batches

The more specific timeline of these batches is defined in Section 4.4.

4.2.2 Ambassador Profiles

The recruited and onboarded ambassadors are from the target stakeholder groups (see Section 2.1); they can be policy makers and regulators, technical innovations, operational practitioners, researchers, private sector professionals, defence sector specialists, and journalists or other influencers, all working with cybersecurity topics. Their main role is to foster stakeholder engagement, communication and dissemination around COcyber, and they can add value to the project from their specific field of activity, especially to the activities running under WP4, such as the public consultations.

Table 8 Relevant Ambassador Profiles

Profile	How their involvement adds value to the COcyber activities?
Policy makers and regulators Government officials, regulatory agency representatives, or legal experts.	These individuals ensure the project considers the critical policies (ex. NIS2, GDPR) and standards in their activities.
Technical innovators Developers of cutting-edge cybersecurity tools or dual-use technologies.	These individuals bring technical insights and foster integration between defence-grade and civilian techno-grade.

<p>Operational practitioners CISOs, Security officer or crisis response leaders from critical sectors (e.g., energy, finance, healthcare).</p>	<p>These individuals can foster the operational expertise perspectives.</p>
<p>Academia & Research Researchers specializing in cybersecurity, risk management, or military–civilian collaboration</p>	<p>These individuals can bring their theoretical knowledge.</p>
<p>Private sector professionals Representatives from SMEs and Start-Ups, or bigger companies in cybersecurity</p>	<p>They advocate for industry–specific needs and can share up-to-date insights from the cybersecurity markets, which contribute to foster the stakeholders’ interest in the project.</p>
<p>Defence sector specialists Representatives from military cyber defence units or national defence agencies.</p>	<p>They provide insights into state-sponsored threats and strategies. These profiles are especially closely linked to our sister project, the ECYBridge¹⁵, activities</p>
<p>Journalists and influencers Journalists, bloggers, and other influence professionals engaged in cybersecurity topics.</p>	<p>These individuals contribute to raising public awareness and to endorse the project’s presence in online / offline media.</p>

4.2.3 Ambassadors’ Duties

To be fit to the ambassador’s position, the ideal ambassador profile is as follows:

- High-level experts engaged in cybersecurity civilian or defence areas, as defined in the section here above.
- Proven activity on social media – at least 2000+ followers across the different social media channels (LinkedIn, Mastodon, BlueSky, Instagram, or Reddit).
- Proven online activity – at least one reference website (e.g., can be the organisation website where the candidate is working).
- Proven impact – scientific or technical publications, engagement in international meetings and/or other relevant stakeholder events.

Figure 16 resumes the key duties of the recruited ambassadors, which all contribute to fostering COcyber’s overall dissemination.

¹⁵ <https://ecybridge.eu/>

COcyber Ambassadors' Mission in 8 points

Figure 16 COcyber Ambassador's mission

Moreover, based on these duties, the COcyber team has defined a list of key performance indicators (KPIs) that the appointed ambassadors are asked to reach by the end of the ambassadorship.

Table 9 Key Performance Indicators for monitoring the ambassadors' mission

Actions to be performed by the Ambassadors	
Action	KPI to be reached
The individual ambassador profiles on the COcyber website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide the necessary information to the COcyber team so they can publish your ambassador profile.
Contribution to an online interview.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Join the COcyber team for a short online interview to present your profile and mission & investment in the cybersecurity sector. Share the produced video on your channels.
Original social media posts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2 original posts on the selected social media channel(s) presenting your involvement to COcyber with personal thoughts & the ambassador programme visual (e.g., banner).
Sharing the COcyber results on social media.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Min. 6 shares of the COcyber results (publications, events, consultations) on the selected social media channel(s).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These postings should be original drafts and not just re-shares from the COcyber posts. • The COcyber team will indicate monthly the results that could be shared and give the draft texts for the posts.
<p>Continuous support activity on social media</p> <p>*The COcyber team will monitor this progress; the ambassadors can only focus on the activity. Check at the mid-term of the ambassadorship.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 likes of COcyber posts. • 15 re-shares of COcyber posts on social media.
<p>Contribution to COcyber’s public consultations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the ambassadorship is active when the COcyber team runs a public consultation on a specific topic, you are invited to provide your inputs (either questionnaire or an interview).
<p>COcyber related event participation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 3 online/offline events (owned or external) around cybersecurity topics. • Provide visibility to COcyber by giving a presentation introducing the project or sharing the project information with participants.
<p>Joining the mid-term and final ambassador programme online meetings.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These meetings with the COcyber team aim to assess the status of the ambassadorship activities and discuss the most recent project updates.

4.3 Selection to the Ambassador Programme

The project’s Milestone 5 is to have “The first round of ambassadors are selected at M6 – December 2024”. To achieve this, the consortium has established a process for scouting and selecting the best candidates.

4.3.1 Eligibility Criteria

The ambassador candidates must:

- Be a **European citizen** based in one of the 27 European countries; we aim to represent the geographical diversity of the European Union among our ambassadors. Also, other criteria, especially gender, bringing more diversity among candidates will be considered.
- Dispose **acknowledged activity, contributions and engagement in the cybersecurity sector** (e.g., scientific publications, job positions, proven technical expertise, contribution to standardisation and/or regulations, publications in specialised journals or magazines, previous mentorship or ambassadorships)
- Have proven **solid online presence**: at least 2000 followers on social media (LinkedIn, BlueSky, Instagram, or Mastodon).
- **Above the age of legal majority.**
- An individual, able to sign the contract with the project.

4.3.2 Scouting and Evaluation Process

For each batch of ambassadors, the project launches a **call for expression of interest**¹⁶ for all candidates, and these are invited to share their spontaneous candidacy via email. In addition, the consortium runs a proactive scouting process of candidates establishing an internal database of relevant profiles. The expression of interest is published preferably 8 weeks before the voting process and is shared via coccyber.eu as well as through the COcyber’s social media channels (LinkedIn and BlueSky).

In parallel, the consortium runs a **proactive scouting of relevant profiles** listing them on a dedicated internal database. All partners are invited to suggest matching profiles from their networks. Based on the final list of candidates, AUS calls the selection committee to process the voting to select a defined number of candidates for each ambassador batch.

In Batch 1, which is now active, the selection committee will run in November 2024 with the aim to **pick up six best scored candidates** based on scoring while considering the general balance and geographical balance. Four profiles will be on a reserve list in case of any of the six best rated ones decline the position.

Considerations on gender balance: we aim to have a balanced representation of all genders in both; the list of identified candidates and the pool of selected ambassadors. According to a report from ECSO (2022)¹⁷ 25% of the cybersecurity workforce are women. COcyber sets this as the minimum threshold for the ambassador programme and aims to go above it.

Considerations on the geographical representation: we aim to have a balanced geographical representation of candidates and selected ambassadors from the key European regions, including Eastern, Northern, Western and Southern regions.

Moreover, the identified candidate profiles will be **rated based on four specific criteria**, including

- a. **Following in social media** – 2,000 followers across different social media (with a focus on LinkedIn) are the minimum eligibility threshold, set that as the baseline (1 point) and scale upwards based on increments that reflect meaningful influence beyond the threshold. The Scoring range goes from 1 to 5 based on the follower numbers of each candidate.

Table 10 Following Score Range

Follower Count Range	Score (1-5)	Interpretation
2,000 – 3,999	1	Minimum eligibility met
4,000 – 6,999	2	Moderate following
7,000 – 10,000	3	Good reach

¹⁶ <https://coccyber.eu/article-news/coccyber-ambassador-programme-strengthening-europes-cybersecurity>

¹⁷ <https://ecs-org.eu/ecso-uploads/2022/10/622f59b70f039.pdf> (consulted 26/11/2024)

10,001 – 20,000	4	Strong influence
20,001+	5	High level of influence or reach

- b. **Fit to the position** – The second evaluation criterion focuses on assessing the candidate’s fit to the position based on the eligibility criteria set (defined in Section Selection to the Ambassador Programme). The minimum threshold is 1 corresponding to limited fit to the position.

Table 11 Fit to the Position Score Range

Score (1-5)	Description of Fit to Position	Interpretation
1	Limited Fit	The candidate meets some minimum criteria but does not significantly align with most position criteria. May lack engagement, visibility, or proven impact within the European cybersecurity sphere.
2	Basic Fit	Meets the minimum eligibility with some alignment to the profile, such as holding a cybersecurity role with limited European focus, or limited stakeholder engagement in the sphere.
3	Moderate Fit	Demonstrates clear engagement in European cybersecurity or related spheres. May have some influence, expertise, and a moderate track record of contributions (e.g., publications or events), but may lack high-profile engagement.
4	Strong Fit	Has a solid European cybersecurity background with a visible public profile. Demonstrates regular and effective engagement with stakeholders, consistent influence, and multiple contributions (e.g., publications, events, media).
5	Exceptional fit	Fully aligns with the set criteria, including high-impact roles in the European cybersecurity field. Shows extensive and ongoing influence, proven impactful contributions, active public engagement, and a high-profile reputation.

- c. **Preference** – Each selection committee member can add one additional point to six candidates of their preference. This point can also help to foster the diversity, scoring to improve the gender balance and/ or the geographic representation.
- d. **Submitted expressions of interest** – Candidates who applied via the expression of interest will obtain one automatic “extra” point to value their motivation.

Once the expression of interest has been running for several weeks gathering spontaneous candidates and the consortium has established a solid list of potential candidates for the ambassador programme, **the selection committee will rate all candidates** with the criteria described here above. This Selection committee is formed by a representative from each partner organisation, including:

- **EITD:** Andrea Lorenzin
- **EOS:** Kristian Reeson

- **ULB:** Georges Ataya
- **LC:** Francesco Mureddu
- **AUS:** Dorina Stanculescu

Once all votes of the selection committee are collected on an internal voting tool, AUS rates the candidates based on the votes from the best scoring ones to the lowest scoring ones. Moreover, based on the batch, the consortium fixes an objective number of ambassadors to be recruited and kept for the reserve list. In each batch, the team runs the selected candidates and reserves lists for the project officer’s approval to avoid any conflicts of interest.

4.4 Ambassador Programme Timeline

The Ambassador programme is organised in three batches: Batch #1 (M7–M12), Batch #2 (M12–M17), and Batch #3 (M19–M24). Between each round, a few weeks are allocated to scouting ambassador profiles, then evaluating the listed candidates and finally contracting the best rated profiles as ambassadors in the project.

General rules for the timeline:

- Each scouting phase will run for 8 weeks.
- The selection committee will gather at the end of the scouting period to vote for the selected candidates.
- Then, EITD will manage the contract (4 weeks) and settle other administrative aspects for the payments.
- Months for the ambassador activity, with KPI monitoring check-ups in M3 and M6.

The timeline planning remains flexible based on the project’s evolving needs and activities. The following three tables provide the initial detailed timeline for each Batch.

Table 12 Ambassadors’ Batch #1 Timeline

Step	Timing (Period M4–M13)
Step 1 – Scouting	October – November 2024
Step 2 – Selection Committee Meeting #1	November 2024
Step 3 – Contracting	December 2024
Step 4 – #1 Ambassadors working	January – June 2025
Step 5 – Mid-term check-up	March 2025
Step 6 – Batch #1 ends & final monitoring of results	June 2025
Step 6 – Final payments to the ambassadors	July 2025

Table 13 Ambassadors’ Batch #2 Timeline

Step	Timing (Period M9–M17)
Step 1 – Scouting	March – April 2025

Step 2 - Selection Committee Meeting #2	April 2025
Step 3 - Contracting	May 2025
Step 4 - #2 Ambassadors working	June - November 2025
Step 5 - Mid-term check-up	August / September 2025
Step 6 - Batch #2 ends & final monitoring of results	November 2025
Step 7 - Final payments to the ambassadors	December 2025

Table 14 Ambassadors' Batch #3 Timeline

Step	Timing (Period M15-M23)
Step 1 - Scouting	September - October 2025
Step 2 - Selection Committee Meeting #3	October 2025
Step 3 - Contracting	November 2025
Step 4 - #3 Ambassadors working	December 2025 - May 2026
Step 5 - Mid-term check-up	February 2026
Step 6 - Batch #3 ends & final monitoring of results	May 2026
Step 7 - Final payments to the ambassadors	June 2026

4.5 Other important aspects

The Ambassador Programmes runs as a part of the COcyber project, and therefore it is aligned to the project’s objectives and responsibilities, as defined in the grant agreement.

4.5.1 Acknowledgement of EU finding and disclaimer

In line with the COcyber project, the ambassadors must use the EU disclaimer and acknowledgement for any original content they might publish as part of their COcyber ambassadorship.

Table 15 Example of the disclaimer for COcyber publications

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre can be held responsible for them."

Also, all materials using the COcyber branding, must be accompanied with the acknowledgement of funding with the two logos

Figure 17 EU Logos for acknowledgement of funding

4.5.2 Conflict of interests

The consortium will prevent the programme from any conflict of interest, and therefore the selection process is openly and clearly defined as well as the evaluation is done by an internal selection committee enabling to count five separate votes.

In addition, the list of final candidates will be shared with the European Commission, and especially the project officer from European Cybersecurity competence centre (ECCC) for their final screening and approval.

4.5.3 Communication about the programme

The ambassador programme has its own logo and visual banners created based on the COcyber branding. This supports the identification of the programme activities and engaged ambassadors.

Figure 18 Ambassador Programme Logo

Figure 19 Ambassador Batch Visual Banners

The external communication about the involved ambassadors will be done through the established communication channels of the project. AUS will create dedicated communication campaigns about the ambassadors and their added value in the project. Also, the COcyber platform will feature the profiles of the recruited ambassadors showcasing their involvement in the community.

The internal communication within the ambassador programme will rely on mailing and regular meetings with the ambassadors. AUS leads this effort. Also, AUS will provide

- A short guideline for the recruited ambassadors (to define clearly the required tangible results and added value/payments).
- A marketing kit to all ambassadors helping them to share the targeted content on their own channels.

5 Exploitation Plan

This report is part of WP5 dedicated to communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement, which all contribute to the overall impact of COcyber. Therefore, the sustainability of the results is highly dependent on successful implementation of the awareness raising, dissemination and engagement activities. In parallel, the work package 6 “Synergies with existing initiatives, exploitation and sustainability” will focus on defining the exploitation and sustainability plans in two dedicated tasks that are both coordinated by EITD, the project’s coordination. These are:

- Task 6.2 Exploitation strategy and activities (M1-M24)
- Task 6.3 Sustainability strategy and activities (M1-M24)

5.1 Key Exploitable Results

The research, community building, and outreach work carried out within the different work packages of the project (WP2–WP6) will result to a set of key exploitable results (KER) for which partners will define tailored exploitation plans to ensure their commercial market uptake, further research and innovation or scientific exploitation. Moreover, each KER will be associated with a dedicated group of COcyber partners, having interests in the specific KERs, for identifying relevant exploitation opportunities.

The initial list of key exploitable results will be shared in a dedicated **deliverable 6.2 COcyber exploitation plan** submitted in M12 by EITD. This report is classified as sensitive to protect the intellectual property of the project partners.

5.2 Exploitation and Sustainability Principles

The COcyber team will refine the plans throughout the project to ensure that the key exploitable results will be exploited in the most optimised manner and that they will remain available and benefit the stakeholders beyond the project’s duration.

In this sense, there are three main exploitation models that COcyber will investigate for its key exploitable results. These models include the following:

Figure 20 Exploitation models

- **Commercial exploitation model**, which implies the paid provision of the project results to the end users, complying with a licensing scheme that will be defined at a later stage.
- **Research exploitation model**, which implies the use of the research know-how acquired in future research activities.
- **Technical exploitation model**, which implies the use of the technological know-how gained for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them.

On the other hand, the sustainability of the project results can be maintained and improved over time. Figure 21 lists the crucial tools that COcyber will implement throughout the project and across the different work packages, which all contribute to sustaining the project’s KERs in time.

Figure 21 Tools to sustain the project in time

Finally, the work package 6 will deliver two reports (both having two iterations), that will provide the specific plans for the project’s exploitation and sustainability:

- **D6.2 COcyber exploitation plan** (M12 and M24, EITD). This is a yearly report to outline the key exploitable results (KERs) of the project and related KPIs as well as present possible ways of exploitation for each of them by the project partners, COcyber community, and stakeholders.
- **D6.3 COcyber sustainability plan** (the first version on M6 and the final version on M24, EITD). Report to present the sustainability approaches that are considered and the action plan for ensuring the continued and systemic impact of the project results in the long term. It also outlines relevant funding and financing options to ensure the continuation of the project’s core activities after the project ends.

6 Conclusion and Next Steps

Under the Digital Europe Programme, funding COcyber, Communication, dissemination, and exploitation plans are structured to ensure that the projects have a sustainable impact even beyond the mere research and innovation outcomes. To this end, COcyber has developed the master plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation, which outlines the most important and critical elements related to these three strategies, that must be considered throughout the entire project lifetime. This document is expected to act as a point of reference for current and foreseen communication and dissemination activities while being continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's lifetime.

AUS oversees the implementation of these activities, monitoring their status as well as the risk assessment and mitigation. To be successful, the project needs firstly, to have continuous and good internal communication, and secondly continuous efforts from the entire consortium, which will help to do attractive and engaging external communication and engagement related to the project's activities and outcomes.

The target stakeholders from the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors across different public and private organisations are at the centre of all activities carried out in this work package. The different targeted engagement tactics will be deployed to involve and inform the stakeholders in COcyber's various outreach activities. A dedicated internal stakeholder database helps to coordinate and map these engagements and widen the outreached contacts throughout the project.

The communication focuses on raising awareness about COcyber's activities and results with the aim to benefit a critical mass of target stakeholders. The mixed portfolio of communication tools and channels combined with a strong brand and project identity ensure the communication is effective and engaging. Now, the project will focus on early bird communication (Phase 2 Communication) designing and implementing targeted communication contents and materials for widening the project's outreach.

The dissemination activities support essentially the project's initiatives on information sharing and knowledge transfer in European civilian and defence digital safety arenas. These include notably participations and organisation of different stakeholders' meetings, events, workshops, consultations, but also, sharing all public research results and recommendations in open access to the widest extent. Now, COcyber will put emphasis on outreach and influence (Phase 2 of Dissemination activities), which include notably convincing more stakeholders to onboard the project's activities and hosting a hackathon.

The COcyber Ambassador programme supports the work package 5 activities; the recruited ambassadors boost the project's outreach and access to new stakeholders. The first batch of ambassadors is now identified; they are rated and selected top-notch professionals from the cybersecurity sectors, and they start working for the project from January 2025 onwards. As the first pilot phase with the ambassadors is done, the related

strategy can be finetuned and adjusted according to the project's needs and raising topics.

Finally, the exploitation plan is closely related to COcyber's communication and dissemination, which all are building blocks for the project's impact beyond its lifetime. The initial exploitation plan will be delivered in M12 by EITD and it's the identified key exploitable results that can be further exploited by the COcyber partners.

Annex 1 – Editorial plan for blog articles in Year 1

Month	Publication date	Type of content	Title	Related campaign group
M13 - July 2025		News / Blog Article	National case studies booklet on cybersecurity technology and information transfer (based on D4.2)	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M13 - July 2025		News / Blog Article	Post-Hackathon Article; key outtakes and insights from the participants.	GET TO KNOW OUR ECOSYSTEM
M13 - July 2025		News / Blog Article	Exploring Dual-Use Technologies and Innovations Deliverable: D4.3 (Knowledge-sharing activities). Focus on dual-use technologies (civilian and defense applications) that COcyber is exploring, highlighting innovations that can benefit both sectors.	WHAT IS COCyber?
M13 - July 2025		Newsletter	Newsletter 4	
M12 - June 2025		News / Blog Article	Presentation of the onboarded ambassadors' batch 2, profiles and contribution	GET TO KNOW OUR ECOSYSTEM
M12 - June 2025		News / Blog Article	A Year in Review: COcyber's Key Milestones and the Road Ahead Deliverable: Provide a year-end review of COcyber's achievements and outline the next steps for 2025.	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M12 - June 2025		News / Blog Article	Hackathon Recap: Innovating for Cybersecurity Solutions Deliverable; spotlighting the top innovations and their potential applications in civil-defense cybersecurity. (based on D5.2)	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M11 - May 2025		Event	Announcement of the COcyber Hackathon: Driving Cyber Innovation, outlining its objectives, themes, and how it promotes civil-defense cooperation in cybersecurity.	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M11 - May 2025		News / Blog Article	Civil-Defense Policy Challenges: Insights from the COcyber Project Deliverable: D4.1 (Guidelines for civil-defense cooperation) Discuss ongoing policy work between civil and defense sectors, offering insights into the challenges and early efforts to harmonize cybersecurity policies.	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M10 - April 2025		News / Blog Article	Update of the Ambassador Programme from Batch 1 (after the M3 monitoring meeting)	GET TO KNOW OUR ECOSYSTEM
M10 - April 2025		Newsletter	Newsletter 3	
M10 - April 2025		News / Blog Article	Introduction to COcyber's dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement strategies (based on D5.1)	WHAT IS COCyber?
M9 - March 2025		News / Blog Article	Call of interest Ambassadors for Batch 2	JOIN THE COcyber ECOSYSTEM
M9 - March 2025		News / Blog Article	Collaboration in Action: Early Milestones in Civil-Defense Cooperation Deliverable: T2.3 (Roadmap & coordination activities) Share insights from early coordination activities, highlighting stakeholder engagement, needs assessment, and the next steps	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M9 - March 2025		News / Blog Article	COcyber Platform: Launching the Hub for Civil-Defense Collaboration Deliverable: D3.1 (COcyber Platform) Celebrate the launch of the platform and detail its functionalities aimed at fostering collaboration between civil and defense sectors.	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M8 - February 2025		News / Blog Article	Our findings from the PESTEL analysis of the cybersecurity sector (based on D4.4)	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M8 - February 2025		News / Blog Article	Discover COcyber secretariat (based on WP2) Focus: Introduce the COcyber Secretariat, explaining its function, its role in bridging civilian and defense sectors, and how it supports policy development.	WHAT IS COCyber?

Month	Publication date	Type of content	Title	Related campaign group
		News / Blog Article	civilian and defense sectors, and how it supports policy development.	WHAT IS COCyber?
		News / Blog Article	Discover the needs assessment for improved participation between cybersecurity civilian and defence fields (based on WP2, D2.2 due in M5)	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M7 - January 2025		Newsletter	Newsletter 2	
M7 - January 2025			Presentation of the onboarded Ambassadors' batch 1, profiles and contribution (based on Milestone 5, M6)	
		News / Blog Article		GET TO KNOW OUR ECOSYSTEM
M7 - January 2025		News / Blog Article	Announcement of the latest edition of the COCyber platform (Based on WP3, Milestone 3, M6)	WHAT HAVE WE ACHIEVED?
M7 - January 2025		News / Blog Article	Community for collaboration (Overview of WP4 & WP5)	WHAT IS COCyber?
M6 - December 2024		Press release	The project in a nutshell & linked to the Press Release on Zenodo	WHAT IS COCyber?
M6 - December 2024		Newsletter	Newsletter 1 – create the news-article inviting to subscribe and read on LinkedIn	
M6 - December 2024		News / Blog Article	Discussions at the GA Hybrid Meeting in Brussels on December 10th	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M6 - December 2024		Event	The ECYBridge Event Article	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M6 - December 2024		Event	ENISA Workshop Article	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M6 - December 2024		Event	COcyber was introduced to the European Deep-Tech Ecosystem	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M5 - November 2024	25/11/2024	Event	COcyber at the 2024 CSDP Annual Training and Education Conference (ATEC)	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M5 - November 2024	19/11/2024	News / Blog Article	COcyber Cybersecurity Platform (Overview of WP3)	WHAT IS COCyber?
M5 - November 2024	14/11/2024	News / Blog Article	COcyber launches focus groups series on cybersecurity collaboration needs	JOIN THE COCyber ECOSYSTEM
M5 - November 2024	04/11/2024	News / Blog Article	Strengthening Europe's Cybersecurity: COcyber's Role in the Evolving EU Framework Introduction to the EU framework around COcyber.	WHAT IS COCyber?
M4 - October 2024	16/10/2024	News / Blog Article	Introduction to the COcyber Ambassador Programme – announcing the call of interest	JOIN THE COcyber ECOSYSTEM
M4 - October 2024	15/10/2024	News / Blog Article	How is the European Union dealing with an evolving cybersecurity landscape?	WHAT IS COCyber?
M4 - October 2024	8/10/2024	News / Blog Article	The COcyber Team Gathers in Brussels to Discuss Milestones Achieved and Future Steps	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M4 - October 2024	1/10/2024	News / Blog Article	Project kickoff meeting about July 24 Kickoff : marks the official launch of the project	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION
M4 - October 2024	13/10/2024	Event	COcyber takes part in the 25th European Security and Defence College (ESDC) EAB.Cyber Meeting	ACTIVITIES, WORKSHOPS, EVENTS AND PARTICIPATION

Annex 2 – Gantt Chart of the Ambassador Programme

Planning for Batch #1

Planning for Batch #2

Planning for Batch #3

